

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AHES	AMI Head End system
API	Application programming interface
BMS	Battery Management System
BRP	Balance Responsible Party
BS	Balance Scheduling
CEM	Customer energy management system
CPO	Charge point operator
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DMS	Distribution management system
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMG	Energy Management Gateway
EV	Electric Vehicle
EVSE	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
FEP	Front End Processor
FO	Flexibility Operator
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IIP	Integrated INVADE Platform
LV	Low Voltage
MDC	Meter Data Concentrator
MDM	Meter data management
MR	Meter Reader
MV	Medium Voltage
NA	Not Applicable
OCHP	Open Clearing House Protocol
OCPI	Open Charge Point Interface
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
OM	Operation meter
OSCP	Open Smart Charging Protocol
PV	Photovoltaic

Acronym	Description
RTU	Remote Terminal Unit
SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
SDC	Smart device controller
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SM	Smart Meter
TBD	To Be Determined
TBS	To Be Specified in D4.3
ToU	Time-of-Use
TSO	Transmission System Operator
USEF	Universal Smart Energy Framework
V2G	Vehicle to Grid
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is part of the WP4 (Overall INVADE architecture), which main objectives are to design the general INVADE system architecture and the software architecture of the Flexibility Cloud as a base for its implementation. In addition, the interface, communication and physical connections of the users to the Flexibility Cloud platform will also be specified.

In particular, this deliverable adapts the generic INVADE architecture described in D4.1 to pilots and describes their specific technical characteristics, components and protocols.

The document starts with an introduction that describes the flexibility services, sources and roles that then are identified and defined for each of the pilots in the following sections. As an example, Table 1 defines the flexibility services that will be implemented in each pilot. The component and communication SGAM layers are also defined for all the pilot sites.

Table 1: Flexibility services to be used in each pilot (Y: yes; N: no, TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Norwegian pilot	Dutch pilots	Bulgarian pilot	German pilot	Spanish pilot
DSO	Congestion management	N	Y	N	Y	Y
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	Y	N	Y	Y
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	Y
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	Y
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	Y
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	kWmax control	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	Self-balancing	Y	Y	Y	Y ¹	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N

The architecture of pilots described in this document will be reviewed and further developed in a second implementation phase in task T4.6. The results of this task will be included in the deliverable D4.3, which will also determine the issues identified with a to be specified label (TBS).

¹ Prosumer self-balancing service is going to be supplied by SMA outside the scope of the INVADE project

The outcomes of this deliverable are an input for WP7 as an input to specify the API functions, for WP8 to define the functionalities and architecture of the INVADE platform, and for WP10 to progress with the pilot specification.

1 Introduction

In D4.1 [1], the general INVADE architecture is described. Using the description of the pilots in task T10.1, this document adapts the INVADE architecture to the different pilot sites. This adaptation needs to take into account the context of every country where the pilot will be set up, the use cases that are going to be demonstrated, and the singularities of each pilot site. For each pilot, the flexibility services, sources and roles are identified in the following chapters. The component and communication SGAM layers are also defined for all the pilot sites. The following sections describe the main characteristics that are specified for each pilot.

1.1 Flexibility services

INVADE platform will be capable of provide several flexibility services to prosumers, DSOs and/or BRPs. These flexibility services are summarized in Table 2. In addition, they are further described in the Deliverables D5.1 [2] and D4.1 [1] of the INVADE project.

Table 2: Flexibility services to be used in INVADE.

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services	Description (Flexibility usage)
DSO	Congestion management	Avoiding the thermal overload of system components by reducing peak loads where failure due to overloading may occur.
	Voltage / Reactive power control	Using load flexibility by increasing the load or decreasing generation is an option to avoid exceeding the voltage limits, typically, when PV systems generate significant amounts of electricity.
	Controlled islanding	Preventing supply interruption in a given grid section when a fault occurs in a section of the grid feeding into it.
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	Shifting loads from a high-price time interval to a low-price time interval before the day-ahead market closure. It enables the BRP to reduce its overall electricity purchase costs
	Intraday portfolio optimization	Enabling value creation on intraday market, equivalent to the day-ahead market
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	Reducing imbalance by the BRP within its portfolio to avoid imbalance charges. The BRP does not actively bid on the imbalance market using its load flexibility, but uses it within its own portfolio.

Prosumer	ToU optimization	Flexibility from high-price intervals to low-price intervals or even complete load shedding during periods with high prices.
	KWmax control	Reducing the maximum load (peak shaving) that the Prosumer consumes within a predefined duration (e.g., month, year), either through load shifting or shedding.
	Self-balancing	Value is created through the difference in the prices of buying, generating, and selling electricity (including taxation if applicable).
	Controlled islanding	Preventing supply interruption in a given customer installation during grid outages.

1.2 Sources

Flexibility in distribution systems can come from different distributed energy resources (DER). They can be grouped by 4 DER types: storage, loads, generation and electric vehicles. Their regulation capability can be up- or downward regulation. Their domain can be customer premises (behind prosumer's smart meter) or directly connected to the LV or MV grid. Finally, according to their power consumption/generation (scale), they can be categorized as low, medium or high flexible power.

Flexibility sources considered in D4.1 [1] and D5.1 [2] are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Flexibility sources covered by INVADE

Classification		Regulation capabilities		Domain			Scale		
Class	Type	Downward regulation	Upward regulation	Customer premises	LV grid	MV grid	Low flexibility	Medium flexibility	High flexibility
Storage control	Battery at households	X	X	X			X		
	Centralized battery (LV grid)	X	X		X			X	X
	Centralized battery (MV grid)	X	X			X		X	X
Load control	Disconnectable load		X	X			X		
	Shiftable load (constant profile)	X	X	X			X		
	Adjustable or shiftable load (constant energy)	X	X	X			X		
Generation control	Disconnectable DER	X		X	X		X		
	Adjustable DER	X	X	X	X		X		
	Disconnectable DER plant	X			X	X		X	X
	Adjustable DER plant	X	X		X	X		X	X
EV control	EV charging station (multiple charging points)		X		X			X	X
	EV charger at household		X	X			X		
	EV public charge point		X		X		X		

	EV charging station with V2G (multiple charging points)	X	X		X			X	X
	EV charger at household with V2G	X	X	X			X		
	EV public charge point with V2G	X	X		X		X		

1.3 Roles

Pilots have four different roles clearly identified and classified by their responsibilities. They are:

1. Balance responsible party (BRP)/ Energy supplier
2. Customers. It includes all DER connected to the grid directly or behind prosumer's smart meter:
 - a. Generation
 - b. Centralized storage
 - c. Electric vehicle charging stations
 - d. Prosumers
3. Flexibility operator (Aggregator)
4. Distribution system operator (DSO)

Figure 1 shows the relation between these four roles. The blue line separates flexibility users and providers. Depending on each flexibility service and business model, flexibility users can be one or another. Additionally, prosumer can be flexibility users and providers at the same time when they are optimizing for their individual purpose. For more information, check D4.1 – section 1.6 application of flexibility to the use cases [1].

These roles are described in the following paragraphs.

- Balance Responsible Party/Energy supplier:

Balance responsible parties (BRP) are the companies required to maintain a continuous balance between the energy demand of their customers and the energy bought in wholesale markets or produced directly [3].

Additionally, Energy suppliers have to provide energy to their customers whenever they need it [4].

Figure 1: Flexibility flow using a centralized operator with external flexibility providers.

- Consumers

‘Active customer’ means a customer or a group of jointly acting customers who consume, store or sell electricity generated on their premises, including through aggregators, or participate in demand response or energy efficiency schemes provided that these activities do not constitute their primary commercial or professional activity (chapter 1, article 2 [5]). In addition, All consumers should be able to benefit from directly participating in the market, in particular by adjusting their consumption according to market signals and in return benefit from lower electricity prices or other incentive payments [5].

- Flexibility Operator

The Flexibility Operator described in D4.2 is covered by the role of an Aggregator in [5]. *‘Aggregator’ means a market participant that combines multiple customer loads or generated electricity for sale, for purchase or auction in any organised energy market (chapter 1, article 2 [5]). In addition, ‘independent aggregator’ means an aggregator that is not affiliated to a supplier or any other market participant (chapter 1, article 2 [5]).*

All customer groups (industrial, commercial and households) should have access to the energy markets to trade their flexibility and self-generated electricity. Customers should be allowed to make full use of the advantages of aggregation of production and supply over larger regions and benefit from cross-border competition. Aggregators are likely to play an important role as intermediaries between customer groups and the market.

Products should be defined on all organised energy markets, including ancillary services and capacity markets so as to encourage the participation of demand response ([5]).

- Distribution System Operator

According to [6] and [5], the 'Distribution system operator' means a natural or legal person responsible for operating, ensuring the maintenance of and, if necessary, developing the distribution system in a given area and, where applicable, its interconnections with other systems and for ensuring the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable demands for the distribution of electricity.

1.4 Implementation phases

In order to implement flexibility services progressively, the INVADE implementation has been divided in two phases. The first phase objective is to collect as much pilot data as possible. This includes generation, flexible loads, electric vehicles, and others depending on each pilot. This information is crucial for further developments during the second phase.

Additionally, the first phase includes the implementation of some flexibility services using simplified algorithms developed in WP5. This phase will end up at mid-term project.

The experience obtained during the first phase will help to improve INVADE algorithms in terms of better forecasting, more advanced functionalities and additional flexibility services.

2 Norwegian pilot

The Norwegian pilot is based on the use of distributed batteries, among other flexibility sources, to reduce the electricity bill and to improve the share of renewables at household level. The main goal of the Norwegian pilot is to demonstrate how the intersection between EV, loads, PV, effect based tariffs and energy management can help to resolve problems that more DER generation in the system lead to. This pilot corresponds to the use cases 1 and 3, which will demonstrate the benefits of distributing energy storage units and EV spread across multiple households.

As described in D10.1, the Norwegian pilot can be divided into 3 different pilot cases:

- **Office:** this case is focused on a great office building, which is the Lyse headquarter.
- **Households:** this case is focused on private households with several homes and known private users.
- **Housing cooperatives:** this case is focused on charging points, possibly in combination with battery banks.

Despite this division, the services and architecture in all pilot cases are equal.

2.1 Flexibility services

Table 4 shows the flexibility services that are going to be implemented in the Norwegian pilot.

Table 4: Flexibility services to be used in the Norwegian pilots (Y: yes; N: no).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Office	Households	Cooperatives
DSO	Congestion management	N	N	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	N	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	N	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	N	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	Y
	kWmax control	Y	Y	Y
	Self-balancing	Y	Y	Y
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N

2.2 Flexibility sources

Table 5 indicates the type of flexibility sources that are going to be used in the Norwegian pilot.

Table 5: Flexibility sources to be used in the Norwegian pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Class	Type	Office	Households	Cooperatives
Storage control	Battery at households/buildings	Y	Y	Y
	Centralized battery at LV grid	N	N	N
	Centralized battery at MV grid	N	N	N
Load control	Disconnectable load	N	Y (water & space heaters)	N
	Shiftable load (constant profile)	N	Y (water & space heaters)	N
	Adjustable or shiftable load (constant energy)	N	Y (water & space heaters)	N
Generation control	Disconnectable DER	Y	Y	N
	Adjustable DER	N	N	N
	Disconnectable DER plant	N	N	N
	Adjustable DER plant	N	N	N
EV control	EV charging station (multiple charging points)	Y	N	Y
	EV charger at household	N	Y	N
	EV public charge point	N	N	N
	EV charging station with V2G (multiple charging points)	N	N	N
	EV charger at household with V2G	N	N	N
	EV public charge point with V2G	N	N	N

2.3 Use of flexibility sources in each service

Table 6 summarizes the use of the different flexibility sources to provide each of the selected services.

Table 6: Use of flexibility sources in each service in the Norwegian pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Load shifting	Load curtailment	Distributed storage control	Centralized storage control	EV control	EV control with V2G	Generation curtailment	Generation increase
DSO	Congestion management	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N
	kWmax control	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N
	Self-balancing	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N

2.4 Roles

Table 7 identifies the parties that will play each role in the Norwegian pilot.

Table 7: Roles in the Norwegian pilot.

Pilot responsible	FO	BRP	DSO
LYSE	LYSE	NA*	NA*

* NA (not applicable) when the role is not involved in the pilot.

2.5 SGAM layers

2.5.1 Component layer

There are three different pilot cases, but regarding the way the information from customer components and the commands are exchanged there is only one architecture definition. The Integrated INVADE platform will communicate through Smartly data HUB at several residential installations, at the Lyse Headquarters, and at EV charging station at housing cooperatives.

The residential installations may have a combination of PV panels, EV-chargers, battery systems and controllable heating/boiler loads, the Lyse Headquarters have a combination of PV, EV-charging and a battery solution with around 200 active users of the system), and the EV charging station at housing cooperatives may also include loads, generation and batteries at a later stage. The Smartly data HUB is capable to communicate and integrate several devices from different providers. Details of the actual service providers and specific devices below Smartly Data HUB remain as an internal business logic as it is considered Smartly business sensitive.

A general component architecture is represented in Figure 2. The component acronyms are described in *Annex 1 - Description of components in the component layer*.

In this pilot, data from customer components will be sent from the Smartly data HUB to the Integrated INVADE platform, where the data is used as input to the flexibility algorithms. Then, from the INVADE platform, control plans per component are returned to the Smartly data HUB, which forwards these to the individual components.

Figure 2: SGAM component layer in the Norwegian pilot.

2.5.2 Communication layer

Figure 3 shows the communication SGAM layer with the protocols used in this pilot. The APIs used between the Integrated INVADE platform and the Smartly Data HUB needs to be defined in WP7. As it is considered in Figure 2, details of the actual protocols used below Smartly Data HUB remain as an internal Smartly business logic.

Figure 3: SGAM communication layer in the Norwegian pilot.

3 Dutch pilot

The Dutch pilot is centred on the use of EV and how they can contribute to balance and strengthen the grid and ensure electricity delivery to the market with as much as possible use of renewable energy. This pilot corresponds to the use case 1, which involves specific business models related to EV-based storage services involving individuals, communities, business establishments, aggregators and DSOs.

As described in D10.1, the Dutch pilot can also be divided into 4 different pilot cases:

- **Large scale offices** and parking lots case, for semi private/public situations and unknown users.
- **Large scale public** case with charge points in the public domain and many unknown users
- **Small scale home** case with several homes and known private users.
- **Small scale public office** case with known users, with solutions that can finally also be used in other public situations, e.g. energy storage and Vehicle 2 Grid.

3.1 Flexibility services

Table 8 shows the flexibility services that are going to be implemented in each of the Dutch pilot cases.

Table 8: Flexibility services to be used in the Dutch pilot (Y: yes; N: no, TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Large scale office	Large scale public	Small scale home	Small scale public & office
DSO	Congestion management	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	Y	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	TBS	TBS	TBS	TBS
	Intraday portfolio optimization	TBS	TBS	TBS	TBS
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	TBS	TBS	TBS	TBS
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	Y	Y
	kWmax control	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Self-balancing	N	N	Y	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N

3.2 Flexibility sources

Table 9 indicates the type of flexibility sources that are going to be used in each of the Dutch pilot cases.

Table 9: Flexibility sources to be used in the Dutch pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Class	Type	Large scale office	Large scale public	Small scale home	Small scale public & office
Storage control	Battery at households	N	N	N	Y
	Centralized battery at LV grid	N	N	N	N
	Centralized battery at MV grid	N	N	N	N
Load control	Disconnectable load	N	N	N	N
	Shiftable load (constant profile)	N	N	N	N
	Adjustable or shiftable load (constant energy)	N	N	N	N
Generation control	Disconnectable DER	N	N	N	N
	Adjustable DER	N	N	N	N
	Disconnectable DER plant	N	N	N	N
	Adjustable DER plant	N	N	N	N
EV control	EV charging station (multiple charging points)	Y	N	N	Y
	EV charger at household	N	N	Y	N
	EV public charge point	N	Y	N	N
	EV charging station with V2G (multiple charging points)	N	N	N	Y
	EV charger at household with V2G	N	N	N	N
	EV public charge point with V2G	N	N	N	N

In the large-scale office, the large-scale public, and small-scale public and office pilot use cases, there are PV generation units. However, they are not controllable, and PV production is only taken as an input to change charging behaviour accordingly.

3.3 Use of flexibility sources in each service

Table 10 summarizes the use of the different flexibility sources to provide each of the selected services.

Table 10: Use of flexibility sources in each service in the Dutch pilot (Y: yes; N: no, TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Load shifting	Load curtailment	Distributed storage control	Centralized storage control	EV control	EV control with V2G	Generation curtailment	Generation increase
DSO	Congestion management	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	TBS	N	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	TBS	N	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	TBS	N	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N
	kWmax control	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N
	Self-balancing	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N

3.4 Roles

Table 11 identifies the parties that will play each role in the different Dutch pilot cases.

Table 11: Roles in the Dutch pilot.

Pilot use case	Pilot responsible	FO	BRP	DSO
Large scale office	Greenflux	Greenflux	TBS*	Several DSOs
Large scale public	ElaadNL	Greenflux	TBS*	Several DSOs
Small scale home	Greenflux	Greenflux	TBS*	Several DSOs
Small scale public & office	ElaadNL	Greenflux	TBS*	Several DSOs

* TBS: to be specified in D4.3.

3.5 SGAM layers

3.5.1 Component layer

In the Dutch pilots, the Integrated INVADE platform communicates with the Greenflux platform and Elaad’s local control box in Greenflux’ and Elaad’s sub-pilots, respectively. Aggregated EV charging data and other load data is sent from the local platforms to the INVADE platform, where the data is used as input to the flexibility algorithms. From the INVADE platform, control plans on an aggregated level are returned to the local platforms. The local platforms are in charge of deciding how the aggregated control plans should be split between the individual pilot components.

Figure 4: SGAM component layer in the large-scale office Dutch pilot.

Figure 5: SGAM component layer in the large-scale public Dutch pilot.

Figure 6: SGAM component layer in the small-scale home Dutch pilot.

Figure 7: SGAM component layer in the small-scale public & office Dutch pilot.

3.5.2 Communication layer

The communication SGAM layers with the protocols used in each pilot case are represented in Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Figure 8: SGAM communication layer in the large-scale office in the Dutch pilot.

Figure 9: SGAM communication layer in the large-scale public Dutch pilot.

Figure 10: SGAM communication layer in the small-scale home Dutch pilot.

Figure 11: SGAM communication layer in the small-scale public & office Dutch pilot.

4 Bulgarian pilot

The Bulgarian pilot is based on the use of a centralized battery in a secondary substation to improve the capacity of renewable generation by optimizing the use of the flexibility provided by this battery and other flexibility sources. This pilot corresponds to the use case 2, with a centralised energy storage in a hotel resort for demand management and power quality improvement.

4.1 Flexibility services

Table 12 shows the flexibility services that are going to be implemented in the Bulgarian pilot.

Table 12: Flexibility services to be used in the Bulgarian pilot (Y: yes; N: no, TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Y/N
DSO	Congestion management	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N
	Controlled islanding	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	TBS
	Intraday portfolio optimization	TBS
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	TBS
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y
	kWmax control	Y
	Self-balancing	Y
	Controlled islanding	N

According to the use case of this pilot, it is suggested to implement the services to the BRP for day-ahead, intraday and self-balancing portfolio optimizations. However, it is possible that Albena changes its energy provider next year, so it is still under discussion that its energy supplier is going to be involved in the project and therefore, that these services can be applied.

The implementation of the controlled islanding inside the prosumer premises is highly dependent on the capabilities of the battery system to be installed. As the battery purchase process is still not finished, the availability of this service in this pilot is still to be determined.

4.2 Flexibility sources

Table 13 indicates the type of flexibility sources that are going to be used in the Bulgarian pilot.

Table 13: Flexibility sources to be used in the Bulgarian pilot (Y: yes; N: no, TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Class	Type	Y/N
Storage control	Battery at households	N
	Centralized battery at LV grid	Y
	Centralized battery at MV grid	N
Load control	Disconnectable load	Y
	Shiftable load (constant profile)	N
	Adjustable or shiftable load (constant energy)	Y
Generation control	Disconnectable DER	Y
	Adjustable DER	N
	Disconnectable DER plant	N
	Adjustable DER plant	N
EV control	EV charging station (multiple charging points)	TBS
	EV charger at household	TBS
	EV public charge point	TBS
	EV charging station with V2G (multiple charging points)	N
	EV charger at household with V2G	N
	EV public charge point with V2G	N

The controlled loads in this pilot corresponds to boilers for domestic hot water. They can be forced to switch on or off for certain amount of time.

In addition, it is planned to install several EV chargers in the Albena resort. However, it is still not clear if they are going to be integrated into the pilot and how they are going to be remotely controlled.

4.3 Use of flexibility sources in each service

Table 14 summarizes the use of the different flexibility sources to provide each of the selected services.

Table 14: Use of flexibility sources in each service in the Bulgarian pilot (Y: yes; N: no, TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Load shifting	Load curtailment	Distributed storage control	Centralized storage control	EV control	EV control with V2G	Generation curtailment	Generation increase
DSO	Congestion management	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	N	Y	TBS	N	Y	N
	kWmax control	Y	Y	N	Y	TBS	N	Y	N
	Self-balancing	Y	Y	N	Y	TBS	N	Y	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N

The implementation of services for the BRP is still to be determined. In case it is possible, shiftable loads, the centralized storage and generation curtailment will be used to offer these services (day-ahead, intraday and self-balancing portfolio optimizations). In addition, the inclusion of controllable EV chargers is still under consideration.

4.4 Roles

Table 15 identifies the parties that will play each role in the Bulgarian pilot.

Table 15: Roles in the Bulgarian pilot.

Pilot responsible	FO	BRP	DSO
Albena	Albena	Energy Market	NA*

* NA (not applicable) when the role is not involved in the pilot.

4.5 SGAM layers

4.5.1 Component layer

Figure 12 shows the component SGAM layer diagram for the Bulgarian pilot. The component acronyms are described in *Annex 1 - Description of components in the component layer*.

Figure 12: SGAM component layer in the Bulgarian pilot.

4.5.2 Communication layer

The communication SGAM layer diagram for the Bulgarian pilot is showed in Figure 13.

Figure 13: SGAM communication layer in the Bulgarian pilot.

5 German pilot

The German pilot corresponds to use case 4, a hybrid of use cases 2 and 3 with a combination of centralized and distributed energy storage units at both substation/street and household levels.

The German pilot focuses as described in D10.1 on two different topics:

- The first pilot case will illustrate that centralised energy storages in areas with weak feeders are an appropriate means to reinforce the grid, ensuring the feed-in of renewable energies and avoiding expensive network expansion. In addition, the pilot intends also to use the flexibility potential of the battery for peak shaving purposes initiated by the DSO.
- The second pilot case examines the opportunities of connecting households consisting of a PV plant and a small-scale battery storage via an existing home management system. Currently, these systems only optimize their self-consumption. The project aims to create additional value by using the untapped flexibility potential of the small-scale batteries to provide peak shaving to the DSO. At least ten households will be connected in the market area of badenova.

5.1 Flexibility services

Table 16 shows the flexibility services that are going to be implemented in the German pilot.

Table 16: Flexibility services to be used in the German pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	DES	CES
DSO	Congestion management	Y	Y
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	Y
	Controlled islanding	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	N	N
	kWmax control	N	N
	Self-balancing	Y ²	N

² Prosumer self-balancing service is going to be supplied by SMA outside the scope of the INVADE project.

Controlled islanding	N	N
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5.2 Flexibility sources

Table 17 indicates the type of flexibility sources that are going to be used in the German pilot.

Table 17: Flexibility sources to be used in the German pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Class	Type	DES	CES
Storage control	Battery at households	Y	N
	Centralized battery at LV grid	N	Y
	Centralized battery at MV grid	N	N
Load control	Disconnectable load	N	N
	Shiftable load (constant profile)	N	N
	Adjustable or shiftable load (constant energy)	N	N
Generation control	Disconnectable DER	N	N
	Adjustable DER	N	N
	Disconnectable DER plant	N	N
	Adjustable DER plant	N	N
EV control	EV charging station (multiple charging points)	N	N
	EV charger at household	Y ³	N
	EV public charge point	N	N
	EV charging station with V2G (multiple charging points)	N	N
	EV charger at household with V2G	N	N
	EV public charge point with V2G	N	N

5.3 Use of flexibility sources in each service

Table 18 summarizes the use of the different flexibility sources to provide each of the selected services.

³ It is planned that two households may include charging points for EVs. They will be compatible with the Sunny Home Manager and controllable via this device.

Table 18: Use of flexibility sources in each service in the German pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Load shifting	Load curtailment	Distributed storage control	Centralized storage control	EV control	EV control with V2G	Generation curtailment	Generation increase
DSO	Congestion management	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	kWmax control	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Self-balancing	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N

5.4 Roles

Table 19 identifies the parties that will play each role in the German pilot.

Table 19: Roles in the German pilot.

Pilot responsible	FO	BRP	DSO	Prosumer
badenova AG & Co. KG	badenova AG & Co. KG	NA*	bnNetze GmbH	Several customers

* NA (not applicable) when the role is not involved in the pilot.

badenova AG & Co. KG is the responsible party for the pilots, the setup of the pilot and the flexibility operator role.

The flexibility of the CES is used exclusively for the purposes of the DSO bnNetze GmbH, which is part of the badenova group. Additionally, the DSO requests and uses aggregated flexibility from the DES in the second pilot case.

5.5 SGAM layers

5.5.1 Component layer

The German pilot consists of two pilot structures with different component layers.

Figure 14 shows the component SGAM layer diagram for the German pilot of distributed energy storages; Figure 15 displays the component SGAM layer diagram for the centralised energy storage. The component acronyms are described in *Annex 1 - Description of components in the component layer*.

Figure 14: SGAM component layer in the German pilot for DES

All test sites will have at least two DER, an uncontrolled PV-system and a small-scale battery. Only two of the test sites will have EV charging points included into their Home Management System.

Figure 15: SGAM component layer in the German pilot for CES

The Operation Meters in Figure 15 indicate so called “energy monitors” which replace smart meters in the German pilot because they are not yet available in Germany. Germany has not launched smart meters across the country so far. The technical capabilities of the devices for the rollout are still lacking. At least three different companies have to get a certification of their communication interface by the Federal Office for Information Security before a nationwide rollout can start.

5.5.2 Communication layer

Figure 16 shows the communication SGAM layer diagram for the German pilot. As the installation of several components are still under discussion, these communications and their integration into the INVADE platform will be defined in the next phases of the project.

Figure 16: SGAM communication layer in the German pilot for DES.

The communication protocols regarding the pilot site with DES are available – as far as they concern the INVADE platform. The connection within the house between the different devices is mainly settled with internal communication protocols from SMA Solar Technology as is not a task within the project. It can be considered as given. The bidirectional dataflow from the house to the INVADE platform is achieved with two data streams:

- Outgoing data stream via the REST-API of Ennex-OS by SMA
- Ingoing data stream via the Coneva gateway

Figure 17: SGAM communication layer in the German pilot for CES.

All communication protocols of the CES pilot regarding the INVADE platform are to be determined together with the hardware supplier Storion and the INVADE project partners.

6 Spanish pilot

The Spanish pilot is based on the use of a centralized battery in a secondary substation to improve the quality of supply in the validation area, where a critical building is placed. In addition, the centralized battery will also be used to improve the capacity of renewable generation by optimizing the use of the flexibility provided by this battery. This pilot corresponds to the use case 2, with a centralised energy storage for demand management and power quality improvement.

6.1 Flexibility services

Table 20 shows the flexibility services that are going to be implemented in the Spanish pilot.

Table 20: Flexibility services to be used in the Spanish pilot (Y: yes; N: no TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Y/N
DSO	Congestion management	Y
	Voltage / Reactive power control	Y
	Controlled islanding	Y
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	TBS
	Intraday portfolio optimization	Y
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	Y
Prosumer	ToU optimization	N
	kWmax control	N
	Self-balancing	N
	Controlled islanding	N

The controlled islanding is confined to a grid area limited by one feeder of the secondary substation where the centralized battery is installed. This feeder supplies the headquarter and the control centre room of EPESA, which power supply has to be maintained under any circumstances.

In addition, the use of the day-ahead optimization service is still under discussion.

6.2 Flexibility sources

Table 21 indicates the type of flexibility sources that are going to be used in the Spanish pilot.

Table 21: Flexibility sources to be used in the Spanish pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Class	Type	Y/N
Storage control	Battery at households	N
	Centralized battery at LV grid	Y
	Centralized battery at MV grid	N
Load control	Disconnectable load	N
	Shiftable load (constant profile)	N
	Adjustable or shiftable load (constant energy)	N
Generation control	Disconnectable DER	Y
	Adjustable DER	Y
	Disconnectable DER plant	N
	Adjustable DER plant	N
EV control	EV charging station (multiple charging points)	N
	EV charger at household	N
	EV public charge point	Y
	EV charging station with V2G (multiple charging points)	N
	EV charger at household with V2G	N
	EV public charge point with V2G	N

EV control will be implemented only in one public charging point at EPESA headquarter with two plugs with on/off and curtailment capabilities.

6.3 Use of flexibility sources in each service

Table 22 summarizes the use of the different flexibility sources to provide each of the selected services.

Table 22: Use of flexibility sources in each service in the Spanish pilot (Y: yes; N: no; TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Load shifting	Load curtailment	Distributed storage control	Centralized storage control	EV control	EV control with V2G	Generation curtailment	Generation increase
DSO	Congestion management	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	N	N	TBS	N	N	TBS	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	kWmax control	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Self-balancing	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N

6.4 Roles

Table 23 identifies the parties that will play each role in the Spanish pilot.

Table 23: Roles in the Spanish pilot.

Pilot responsible	FO	BRP	DSO
EPESA	MERCATOR	MERCATOR	EPESA

6.5 SGAM layers

6.5.1 Component layer

The component SGAM layer diagram for the Spanish pilot is showed in Figure 18. The component acronyms are described in *Annex 1 - Description of components in the component layer*.

Figure 18: SGAM component layer in the Spanish pilot.

6.5.2 Communication layer

The communication SGAM layer diagram for the Spanish pilot is showed in Figure 19.

Figure 19: SGAM communication layer in the Spanish pilot.

As the installation of distributed batteries and PV panels are still under discussion, these communications and their integration into the INVADE platform will be defined in a second deployment phase of the project. It will be described in D4.3 – Overall INVADE architecture final.

7 Conclusions

After collecting all information from pilots and describing their architectures using the SGAM, the following tables summarize the main points for further stages and other WPs.

Table 24 is a comparison between flexibility services implemented in INVADE and tested in each pilot.

Table 24: Flexibility services to be used in each pilot (Y: yes; N: no; TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Norwegian pilot	Dutch pilots	Bulgarian pilot	German pilot	Spanish pilot
DSO	Congestion management	N	Y	N	Y	Y
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	Y	N	Y	Y
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	Y
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	TBS
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	Y
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	TBS	TBS	N	Y
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	kWmax control	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	Self-balancing	Y	Y	Y	Y ⁴	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N

Nevertheless, the implementation of all these services requires a significant amount of time and resources. In order to grow progressively, implementation efforts should be split in two phases. The first and the second stages should end by mid-2018 and mid-2019 respectively.

Optimization algorithms and services to be provided in the two implementation phases are:

- 1st phase: Prosumer services (ToU, kWmax and self-balancing)
- 2nd phase: BRP services + DSO services + improvements in the services implemented during the 1st phase

Table 25 shows which pilots will include each flexibility service at the end of the first phase.

⁴ Prosumer self-balancing service is going to be supplied by SMA outside the scope of the INVADE project

Table 25: Flexibility services to be implemented in phase 1 in each pilot (Y: yes; N: no).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Norwegian pilot	Dutch pilots	Bulgarian pilot	German pilot	Spanish pilot
DSO	Congestion management	N	N	N	N	N
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	N	N	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	N	N	N	N
Prosumer	ToU optimization	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	kWmax control	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	Self-balancing	Y	Y	Y	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N

In contrast, Table 26 shows the new flexibility services implemented during the second phase of INVADE project.

Table 26: Flexibility services to be implemented during phase two in each pilot (Y: yes; N: no; TBS: to be specified in D4.3).

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Norwegian pilot	Dutch pilots	Bulgarian pilot	German pilot	Spanish pilot
DSO	Congestion management	N	Y	N	Y	Y
	Voltage / Reactive power control	N	Y	N	Y	Y
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	Y
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	N	Y	TBS	N	TBS
	Intraday portfolio optimization	N	Y	TBS	N	Y
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	N	Y	TBS	N	Y
Prosumer	ToU optimization	2 nd iteration	2 nd iteration	2 nd iteration	N	N
	kWmax control	2 nd iteration	2 nd iteration	2 nd iteration	N	N
	Self-balancing	2 nd iteration	2 nd iteration	2 nd iteration	N	N
	Controlled islanding	N	N	N	N	N

The coexistence of different platforms in INVADE project requires to specify the tasks of each platform and pilot. Table 27 exposes which pilots and platforms will take decisions considering flexible sources aggregated or individually.

Table 27: Allocation of optimization algorithms in each platform.

Flexibility services INVADE	Norwegian pilot	Dutch pilots	Bulgarian pilot	German pilot	Spanish pilot
Aggregated optimization algorithm	eSmart	eSmart	eSmart	eSmart	eSmart
Individual optimization algorithm		Greenflux / Elaad		SMA	

Finally, Table 28 shows which company will take each role in each pilot.

Table 28: Roles in each pilot.

Pilot	Pilot responsible	FO	BRP	DSO
Norwegian	LYSE	LYSE	NA*	NA*
Dutch	Greenflux / ElaadNL	Greenflux	TBS**	Several DSOs
Bulgarian	Albena	Albena	Energy Market	NA*
German	badenova AG & Co. KG	badenova AG & Co. KG	badenova AG & Co. KG	bnNetze GmbH
Spanish	EPESA	MERCATOR	MERCATOR	EPESA

* NA (not applicable) when the role is not involved in the pilot.

* TBS: to be specified in D4.3.

The architecture of pilots described in this document will be reviewed and further developed in task T4.6. The results of this task will be included in the deliverable D4.3, which will also determine the issues identified with a to be specified label (TBS).

8 References

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9 Annex 1 - Description of components in the component layer

Table 29 and Table 30 contain descriptions of the components that will be used to define the component layer in the INVADE project. While Table 29 shows the description of the components previously introduced in D4.1 [1] in the generic component layer, Table 30 describes new components used in the adaptation of the generic architecture to each pilot.

Table 29: Description of components present in the INVADE generic component layer.

Name	Description
Aggregation function of the flexibility operator	It manages all transactions and workflows necessary to aggregate and implement flexibility services. It includes energy scheduling, settlement, billing and accounting applications, and it takes care of the actions related to the DSO/BRP-FO interactions. It is also equipped with prediction and big data analytics.
Balance scheduling (BS)	Application that plans the energy procurement of a balance responsible energy retailer to satisfy the energy demands of their customers.
Customer energy management system (CEM)	Energy management system for energy customers to optimize the utilization of energy according to supply contracts or other economic targets.
Charge point operator (CPO)	It is responsible for supplying, installing, maintaining and repairing the charging points.
Distributed energy resource (DER)	A small unit that generates or consumes energy. It includes generation and storage connected to the distribution grid.
DER controller	Controller of a DER that allows the adjustment of its active or reactive power output according to a received set point.
Distribution management system (DMS)	Application server of a Distribution Operator which hosts applications to monitor and control a distribution grid from a centralized location, typically the control centre. A DMS typically has interfaces to other systems, like a GIS or an OMS.
Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE)	Single or multiple power outlets specially designed to charge the battery of cars. Typically including also facilities meter the energy consumption and to authenticate the owner of the car to be charged for settlement reasons.
Energy Management Gateway (EMG)	Gateway used to interface the private area with remote service providers and also with the metering system.
Electric vehicle (EV)	A vehicle with an electric drive (as only drive or in combination with a fuel engine) and a battery which can be charged at a charging station.
Front End Processor (FEP)	System component in charge of interfacing widely spread remote sub/systems or component usually communicating over WAN, to a central database.
Meter reader (MR)	Device which measures the energy consumption within predefined cycles from the smart meter. The metered energy consumption is used to determine the energy bill. It is not used by the DSO.
Operation function of the	It is in charge of managing the orders and schedules that the flexibility plan defines. It receives requests from the aggregator and allocates flexibility at device level.

flexibility operator	
Operation meter (OM)	Device which monitors the energy consumption of a specific device for operational and control reasons. It is placed beyond the main meter, The meter values are not used for commercial purposes.
Smart device	It includes loads and customer appliances that provide an interface to influence their consumption behaviour. It can also include generation, storage and electric vehicles placed at customer premises.
Smart device controller (SDC)	Control the energy consumption of a smart device according to received set point without jeopardizing the desired process of the device.
Smart meter (SM)	Electronic device that measures and records consumption of electric energy in intervals of an hour or less and communicates that information at least daily back to the utility for monitoring and billing. It measures aggregated consumptions of customers.

Table 30: Description of components not present in the INVADE generic component layer.

Name	Description
AMI Head End system (AHES)	A system which acts as back-end for the metering communication and controls and monitors the communication to the meter devices. The collected meter information is provided for other system like meter data management.
Battery Management system (BMS)	Any electronic system that manages a rechargeable battery, such as by protecting the battery, monitoring its state, calculating secondary data, reporting that data and / or balancing it.
Centralized storage (a type of DER)	A type of DER that consist of an electrical energy storage which is installed behind the meter point.
Distributed storage (a type of DER)	A type of DER that consist of an electrical energy storage which is installed behind the meter point.
Intelligent Electronic Device (IED)	It includes equipment to protect, control and monitor the process of the electrical network.
Meter Data Concentrator (MDC)	Device or application typically in a substation which establishes the communication to smart meters to collect the metered information and send it in concentrated form to an AMI head end.
Meter data management (MDM)	Meter Data Management system is a system or an application which maintains all information to be able to calculate the energy bill for a customer based on the meter data retrieved from AMI head end(s).
Remote Terminal Unit (RTU)	A microprocessor-controlled electronic device that interfaces objects in the physical world to a distributed control system or SCADA by transmitting telemetry data to the system.